

Development of hydride-based coupled systems for the hydrogen economy

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Abstract

Hydrogen as an energy carrier can be used to implement power-to-gas-to-power (PtoGtoP) concepts on a large scale and for long periods of time to balance supply and demand to achieve carbon neutrality goals. However, challenges remain, such as intermittent energy inflows, high cost, and low energy efficiency (15 to 40%) due to energy conversion and storage losses [1]. An energy-efficient and compact solution for hydrogen storage is metal-hydrogen compounds, so-called metal hydrides (MH): compared to high-pressure hydrogen storage, twice the volumetric hydrogen density ($> 50 \text{ kg H}_2/\text{m}^3$) is achieved at much lower pressures, typically less than 50 bar [1,2], thus also wasting less energy as compared with high pressure or liquid storage. In this work, an overview of the development and results from the Digi-HyPro project (Digitized Hydrogen Process Chain for the Energy Transition) is presented. It shows the design and progress of a scale-up test system named 20KSYS (20 kWel power at a maximum efficiency integrated metal hydride-electrolyzer and fuel cell). This system includes an electrolyzer system (ELS), a fuel cell system (FCS), a metal hydrogen storage system (MHSS), a battery system (BATS), a heat management system (HMS), interphases for photo voltaic panels (PVP) and integration into electromobility via a bidirectional plug (BWB & P). This comprehensive setup allows the evaluation of all perspective energy conversion processes and aims to demonstrate improvements in energy efficiency for the different operation modes.

Keywords: *Green Hydrogen, Hydrides, Storage, Fuel Cell, Electrolyzer, Coupling*

References

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Biography

Dr. Julián Puszkiel has more than ten years of experience in different fields of materials science, applications of hydrogen, energy technology, and capture-conversion CO₂ (h-index: 24 / citations > 1800). He has been in eight different positions in research centers in Argentina, Spain, and Germany obtained through competitive evaluation processes in the frame of different agencies and institutions such as CONICET, Alexander von Humboldt, and EU-Marie Skłodowska-Curie-ACCIÓ. He is the head of the laboratory in the Dept. of Applied Material Engineering at Helmut-Schmidt-University Hamburg and deputy head of the Dept. of System Design for Mobile and Stationary Hydrogen-Energy Applications in Helmholtz-Zentrum HEREON, Germany.